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COVER ART – Breaching Mosasaur - Illustration by Dr. Zack Boles of Rowan University.

SCOYENIA ICHNOFACIES OF THE LANCE FORMATION IN ELK BASIN, PARK COUNTY, WYOMING, USA

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ABSTRACT - Despite a long history of paleontological exploration and an extensive list of vertebrate fossils recorded in the Lance Formation, trace fossils have been rarely described in this unit. This paper describes an invertebrate ichnofossil assemblage collected in Elk Basin in Park County, Wyoming during 2013 and 2014 summer fieldwork conducted by the New Jersey State Museum. NJSM 24296 contains a suite of traces from *Scoyenia* ichnofacies and includes 31 ichnites identified as *Taenidium satanassi* and three as ichnogenus *Camborygma*. These traces, which are interpreted as arthropod and crayfish burrows, respectively, along with asymmetrical ripple marks, support a shallow fluvially dominated paleoenvironment for this location during the Latest Cretaceous.

INTRODUCTION

The Lance Formation (Elk Basin, Park County, Wyoming, USA) contains one of the best-known Late Cretaceous vertebrate faunas (e.g., Hatcher, 1893; Hatcher et. al., 1907; Archibald, 1996; Estes, 1964; Clemens, 1960, 1963, 1966, 1973; Derstler, 1994; Breithaupt, 1982, 1985; Whitmore, 1985; Whitmore and Martin, 1986; Webb, 1998, 2001). The fauna contains cartilaginous and bony fishes, frogs, salamanders, champsosaurs, turtles, lizards, snakes, crocodiles, pterosaurs, mammals, birds, and some of the best known Cretaceous dinosaurs including *Triceratops*, *Leptoceratops*, *Torosaurus*, *Tyrannosaurus*, *Edmontosaurus*, *Pachycephalosaurus*, *Ankylosaurus*, *Edmontonia*, *Thescelosaurus*, *Troodon*, *Dromaesaurus*, and *Ornithomimus*. Comparatively speaking, the invertebrate (e.g., Stanton 1920, 1947) and botanical (Knowlton, 1922 and Dorf, 1942) components of the Lance Formation fossil biota have been documented to a lesser extent. Similarly, there have been a few reported trace

fossils from this formation. Lockley (2004) reported on diverse dinosaur/bird footprint assemblage in this unit, but very few other records of trace fossils exist. This paper reports on a suite of invertebrate traces from the Lance Formation, with implications for its paleoenvironmental setting.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The Lance Formation encompasses approximately 3 million years of geologic time at the end of the Maastrichtian, the top of which has been dated to ~69 million years ago and extends to the K-Pg boundary. The formation is interpreted to represent deposition in a temperate to subtropical, seasonal floodplain on the west coast of an eastward-regressing inland seaway. It is dominated by non-marine, coastal floodplain sandstones and mudstones with marginal marine sandstones and shales presented in the stratigraphically lower portions. The physical environment and biotic diversity is interpreted to

be most similar to the subtropical portions of the Gulf Coastal Plain of the southeastern United States of today. Both environments support a diverse biota, including crocodylians, soft-shelled turtles, sirens, gars, and bowfins in an ecosystem dominated by lush lowland vegetation among meandering streams with coastal connections, and areas of occasional ponding with seasonal water restrictions (Breithaupt, 1982; Russell, 1989). In fact, the Late Cretaceous Lance Formation is one of the most fossiliferous units in Wyoming (Breithaupt, 1997). The paleontological significance of this unit was first noted in 1872 with the discovery of a partial skeleton of a dinosaur from the western part of the state (Breithaupt, 1982; 1994).

The Bighorn Basin (**Figure 1**) is an arid, intermontane basin in north central Wyoming. Trending northwest-southeast, it is approximately 100 km long and 60 km wide, with the

northernmost topographic expression of the basin terminating just across the Montana border near Red Lodge. Within the structural basin lies numerous secondary basins, including northern Wyoming's Elk Basin.

The trace fossils discussed in this paper are from the Lance Formation, which consists of non-marine, primarily fluvial, sediments that outcrop in Colorado, Wyoming, and Montana. The Lance represents the terminal Cretaceous (Maastrichtian) sediments in the Big Horn basin of Wyoming and is overlain by the Paleocene fluvial sediments of the Fort Union Formation. The ichnofossils described herein were collected from a locality informally named "Camburn Canyon" by the New Jersey State Museum (NJSM) paleontology expedition teams that visited the site from 2001 to 2016. Camburn Canyon is located within Elk Basin, and details of the location are kept on file at the NJSM.

Figure 1: Bighorn Basin

BACKGROUND

The *Scoyenia* (White, 1929) ichnofacies (Figure 2) was proposed by Seilacher (1967) and later refined by Buatois and Mangano (1995, 2012). It

is generally characterized by: (1) abundance of horizontal meniscate backfilled traces produced by mobile deposit feeders (e.g., "ichnogenus name(s)"); (2) abundance of locomotion traces, including both trackways and bilobate trails; (3)

presence of vertical domiciles; (4) a mixture of invertebrate (mostly arthropod), vertebrate and plant traces; (5) low to moderate ichnodiversity; and (6) localized high abundance. This ichnofacies is generally found in non-marine sandstones and shales (Buatois and Mangano 2012) and includes meniscate traces, arthropod trackways and bilobed traces. The *Scoyenia* (White, 1929) Ichnofacies is characterized by a low diversity trace fossil assemblage consisting primarily of simple horizontal fodinichnia (feeding traces), which are formed as organisms disturb the sediment in search of food. *Scoyenia* (White, 1929) and *Taenidium* Heer 1877 are the typical fodinichnia traces represented within the *Scoyenia* (White, 1929) ichnofacies. The ichnofacies also occasionally includes domichnia, (burrows interpreted as dwelling structures) that are often represented by terrestrial *Skolithos* (Haldemann, 1840) and *Camborygma* Hasiotis, Mitchell, 1993 ichnofossils. Repichnia, or tracks that show evidence of locomotion, are also found, and are often produced by insects or freshwater shrimp. In the *Scoyenia* (White, 1929) Ichnofacies, repichnia ichnofossils are most commonly represented by ichnogenus *Cruziana* d'Orbigny, 1842 and *Isopodichnu* Brady 1947. The ichnogenus *Taenidium* Heer 1877 and *Camborygma* Hasiotis, Mitchell, 1993 are

represented in the *Scoyenia* ichnofacies reported herein.

The ichnogenus *Taenidium* Heer 1877 consists of unlined, unbranched, straight to sinuous burrows composed of thick backfills symmetrical about the axis of the burrow (D' Alessandro and Bromley, 1987). The backfill texture may be heterogeneous, homogeneous or pelleted. There are three recognized ichnospecies based on the backfill morphology. *T. serpentium* Heer 1877 have regularly spaced, texturally homogeneous, meniscate backfills with thickness that approaches the diameter of the burrow. *T. cameronensis* Brady, 1947 have backfill which are deeply arcuate and much thicker than the burrow width. *T. santanassi* D'Alessandro, Bromley, 1987 consists of thick, regularly spaced pelleted meniscate backfills (see Figure 5). The direction of movement is in the direction in which the meniscate marks bend, upwards in Figure 5.

The ichnogenus *Camborygma* Hasiotis, Mitchell, 1993 consists of subvertical to subhorizontal shafts that range from 1-14 cm in diameter and extend vertically up to 9 m. Burrow walls may contain scratch marks, scrape marks, knobby textures, and striations. *Camborygma* Hasiotis, Mitchell, 1993 is often interpreted as representing freshwater crayfish burrows,

Figure 2: *Scoyenia* Ichnofacies (Buatois & Mangano, 2012)

DESCRIPTION

The ichnofossils were collected from a block of reddish sandstone, approximately 250 x 150 cm in size, which is broken into 18 subequal sections. Due to space and weight restrictions, and an abundance of ichnofossils concentrated on the single largest slab, only the left most slab in

Figure 3 was collected (NJSM 24296) by the authors in 2013. The entire block of 18 subequal sections have numerous asymmetrical ripple marks on them, and upon those are superimposed 34 traces fossils (Table 1; Figs. 4. 5 and 6). Thirty-one of these are characterized by being horizontal, meniscate traces. The other three are identified as vertical borings.

Figure 3: Complete Assemblage of 18 sections. NJSM 24296 is the leftmost section.

DISCUSSION

The sandstone block shows several of the identifying features of the *Scoyenia* ichnofacies including horizontal meniscate backfilled traces, vertical domiciles, low ichnodiversity and localized high abundance. The slab contains numerous asymmetrical ripple marks overlain by 34 trace fossils from the *Scoyenia* Ichnofacies. Thirty-one of the traces are thick, regularly spaced, pelleted, meniscate backfills made on the vertical plain of the sandstone block. The other trace consists of three circular, backfilled burrows, made horizontal to the block. These trace

fossils are interpreted as belonging the *Scoyenia* (White, 1929) Ichnofacies. The meniscate traces are identified as *Taenidium satanassi* D'Alessandro, Bromley, 1987 and vertical burrows are identified as *Camborygma* isp. Figure 4 is a field map of the entire set of associated slabs with the tracks labeled A-Z, AA-EE

Table 1 provides the length and width of each of the thirty-one meniscate traces and Table 2 provides measurement for the backfilled burrow

Table 1: Measurements of 32 of *Taenidium satanassi* D'Alessandro, Bromley, 1987 traces found in the sandstone bed shown in Figure 4. All measurements in cm.

Label	Slab	Quadrant	Length x Width
A	1	A2	14 x 1
B	1	B3	5.5 x 1
C	1	B3	7.5 x 1
D	1	B3	7 x 1
E	1	B3	17.5 x 1.5
F	1	B3	9 x 1
G	2	B1	7 x 0.4
H	4	C2	10.5 x 7
I	4	C2	5.5 x 1
J	4	C3	11 x 0.5
K	4	C3	13 x 0.6
L	4	C3	4 x 0.6
M	5	C2	4.7 x 0.8
N	9	D2	8.5 x 1
O	7	C3	5.6 x 0.8
P	7	D3	31 x 0.8
Q	18	D3	4.5 x 0.8
R	11	D2	21.5 x 0.7
S	8	D2	14 x 0.8
T	8	D2	10 x 1
U	8	D3	6.5 x 1.2
V	14	D2	4 x 0.5
W	1	B3	3.5 x 0.7
X	1	B3	4 x 1.2
Y	4	C3	2 x 0.5
Z	5	C2	3.5 x 1
AA	1	B3	5.5 x 1
BB	4	C3	4 x 1
CC	12	D1	8 x 1
EE	16	E3	3.5 x 0.5
FF	16	E2	3 x 1

Table 2: Measurements of *Camborygma isp.*

Label	Slab	Quadrant	Length x Width (CM)
DD	12	D1	Circular tops of 3 closely spaced borrow, 0.4 CM diameter

The asymmetrical ripple marks are current-formed ripples with long and relatively straight crests, some of which are truncated by subsequent flows. These ripples indicate shallow

water along a sandy shore with weak currents. The ripples have an average wavelength of 3 cm with an average height of 0.4 cm.

Figure 4: The ripple marks on the 18 subequal sections are shown in this field map as contour lines with perpendicular hash marks indicating the current direction.

ICHNOTAXONOMY

Taenidium santanassi D'Alessandro and Bromley 1987 Figs. 5,6

Occurrence - *Taenidium santanassi* D'Alessandro and Bromley 1987 is the most abundant trace in the slab; 31 / 32 traces. Traces P, S, N and R could be interpreted as one long *Taenidium* (Heer, 1877) trace measuring 75 cm in length, fragmented into parts when the entire red sandstone slab split into smaller pieces

Paleoenvironmental significance – *Taenidium* (Heer, 1877) is traditionally interpreted to represent burrows made by arthropods, but Annelids are also potential tracemakers. Smith et. al. (2008) states that all three ichnospecies in the ichnogenus *Taenidium* (Heer, 1877) have only been described from marine environments. However, Buatois and Mangano (2012) indicate that *Taenidium* (Heer, 1877) is found in both continental and marine environments.

Figure 5: *Taenidium satanassi* D'Alessandro and Bromley 1987 (from Smith, et al., 2008)

Figure 6: *Taenidium satanassi* D'Alessandro and Bromley 1987 traces

***Camborygma isp.* Hasiotis, Mitchell, 1993 Fig. 7**
Occurrence – *Camborygma* Hasiotis, Mitchell, 1993 is represented by the circular tips of three burrows labelled DD in NJSM 24296. See Figure 7.

Paleoenvironmental significance: – The ichnogenus *Camborygma* Hasiotis, Mitchell, 1993 is interpreted to represent crayfish burrows, and crayfish inhabit only fresh water environments.

Figure 7: *Camborygma* isp. Hasiotis, Mitchell, 1993

CONCLUSION

Despite a long history of investigation and a thoroughly studied vertebrate fauna, the invertebrate ichnology of the Lance Formation is less well documented. Our findings fill this gap by describing 31 specimens of *Taenidium satanassi* D'Alessandro and Bromley 1987 and three specimens of *Camborygma* Hasiotis, Mitchell, 1993 from a single exposure. Superimposed on asymmetrical ripple marks, these biogenic structures support a shallow, subaqueous, non-marine, primarily fluvial, paleoenvironmental interpretation of the Lance formation.

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